

1 **Oligodendrocyte and myelin program genes associated with lineage commitment to the TE in**
2 **humans.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of
9 oligodendrocyte and myelin program genes associated with lineage commitment to the TE in humans. The
10 TE myelin program included MAG, Nsmf, Smpd3a/b, Oligophrenin and a non-coding RNA, OLMALINC.

11 Citations

12 1. Kondo, T. and Raff, M., 2000. Oligodendrocyte precursor cells reprogrammed to become
13 multipotential CNS stem cells. Science, 289(5485), pp.1754-1757.